

Guideline

for Integrating Diversity and Inclusion
in Geography and Science Education

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Guideline factsheet & imprint

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Guideline for Integrating Diversity and Inclusion in Geography and Science Education

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Abstract

This guideline for teacher trainers presents an inclusive teaching approach for geography and science education within the V-GeoSciEd project. Central to the framework is the MODI model (Model for integrating Diversity and Inclusion), which promotes awareness of diversity and enables inclusive learning based on Universal Design for Learning (UDL) principles. The guidelines encompass theoretical foundations, curricular considerations, practical implementation, and evaluation methods. Additionally, case studies from geography and science education illustrate strategies to create diverse and equitable learning environments. The aim is to support teacher trainers in developing and implementing inclusive teaching concepts effectively.

1

Introduction

V-GeoSciEd offers an inclusive teaching approach that enables teacher trainers to engage all students, regardless of background, in meaningful learning activities based on the concept of Universal Design for Learning (UDL). It is a widely accepted concept that is studied and implemented around the world in different contexts, such as schools, universities and workplaces.

UDL is a framework designed to improve and optimise teaching and learning for all people (Hall, Meyer & Rose 2012; 2024; Meyer, Rose & Gordon 2014). It is based on research into how people learn, recognising that learners differ in the ways they perceive and engage with information. UDL seeks to create supportive, flexible, and inclusive learning environments that accommodate these differences from the outset rather than adapting teaching later. UDL will be discussed in detail in section 2.3.

The main goal of UDL is to ensure high-quality educational practices and equitable access to learning for everyone, by considering the heterogeneous starting points of every student.

UDL is structured around three core principles, often described as the “**Why, What, and How of learning**”:

Engagement

The **WHY** of learning

Representation

The **WHAT** of learning

Action and Expression

The **HOW** of learning

UDL promotes inclusive and adaptable teaching practices that recognise learner variability as a strength, ensuring that all individuals can reach their full potential through equitable educational opportunities.

The following guideline provides a systematic overview of the measures required to successfully take diversity into account and to design inclusive learning environments accordingly. It offers specific suggestions on how the model can be used in teacher training and presents examples of how UDL principles can be applied when planning geography and science lessons. The main target group is teacher trainers, who can also use the guidelines themselves for in-service and pre-service teacher training.

2

Model for integrating Diversity and Inclusion in Geography and Science Education (MODI)

The V-GeoSciEd model, known as MODI, supports teachers to embed diversity and inclusion within their lessons. It aims to equip geography and science educators across Europe with the tools and training to create inclusive, diverse, and sustainable learning environments. As shown below, the model follows a cyclical and progressive process comprising four interrelated phases (see figure 1).

Guideline: Model for the integration of diversity and inclusion in geography and science education

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Figure 1: Model for integrating Diversity and Inclusion in Geography and Science Education (Own illustration, Graphic: UHH / Martinez Corrales)

Download: → <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19076003>

- In the first phase, **Conception and Understanding**, teachers reflect on their own views and conceptualisations of diversity and inclusion by studying and discussing academic literature.
- In the second phase, **Intended Curriculum**, teachers integrate diversity-sensitive content that reflects learners' needs and prior experiences, whilst promoting inclusion within educational programmes through participation in working groups or curriculum development committees.
- In the third phase, **Practice and Implementation**, the focus is on creating inclusive classroom environments, developing practical teaching skills, and applying accessible and diverse strategies and materials.
- Finally, in the **Evaluation and Further Development** phase, continuous improvement is ensured through student feedback and peer observation, fostering an educational culture that is equitable, inclusive, and responsive to diversity.

2.1 Conception and understanding

The Conception and Understanding phase addresses the growing need for equitable and inclusive educational practices that empower both teachers and learners. It begins by

clarifying personal concepts, ensuring a shared understanding of essential terms and principles relating to diversity and inclusion within the UDL framework.

2.1.1 Initial Conceptualisations and Understanding of Diversity and Inclusion

- ➔ **Topic:** Personal understanding of diversity and inclusion
- 🔄 **Objective:** Clarify personal interpretations of diversity and inclusion in education
- ✍️ **Task:** In-service or pre-service teachers reflect on their own ideas about diversity and inclusion, share these with a partner, and develop a shared understanding as a foundation for deeper engagement with key concepts (Think-Pair-Share).

1. Think – Individual Reflection

- Reflect on your personal understanding of diversity and inclusion. What do these terms mean to you? What images, experiences, or thoughts do you associate with them?
- Note down keywords, short sentences or sketches.

2. Pair – Partner Discussion

- Partner A shares their ideas; Partner B listens actively. Then roles switch.
- Goal: Develop mutual understanding and identify similarities and differences.
- **Guiding questions:**
 - What do you understand by diversity and inclusion?
 - Why are these terms important to you?
 - Were there any surprises in your partner's responses?

3. Share – Group Presentation / Plenary Discussion:

- Each pair briefly presents their main insights.
- **Collective reflection:** How are the terms used? What is the core message? What similarities and differences emerge in understanding?

Materials:

- Worksheets with three reflective questions or space for individual thinking
- Flipchart or whiteboard for key concept definitions
- Notepads or Post-it notes for sharing and note-taking

2.1.2 Concepts of diversity and inclusion in scientific literature

→ **Topic:** Concepts in Scientific literature

🔄 **Objective:** Engage with diversity and inclusion concepts through scientific literature.

📌 **Task:**

a) Work with selected scientific literature on diversity and inclusion

OECD (2023), *Equity and Inclusion in Education: Finding Strength through Diversity*,
OECD Publishing,
Paris, pp. 1 – 53

→ <https://doi.org/10.1787/e9072e21-en>

- Read the selected text. What core messages can you identify?
- To what extent does this change or expand your understanding
- Use the following questions to guide your reflection

Comprehension

- What does the text mean by diversity?
- How is inclusion defined in the text?
- What types of diversity are mentioned?
- Why is inclusion considered important according to the text?
- What examples of inclusive practices are given?

Analysis

- What problems can arise from a lack of inclusion, according to the text?
- Does the text distinguish between equality and equity?
- What arguments does the author use to emphasise the value of diversity?

Reflection and Discussion

- In which areas of everyday life is inclusion especially important?
- What challenges to inclusion are mentioned in the text?
- Do you agree with the ideas presented in the text? Why or why not?

Application and Transfer

- How can the ideas from the text be applied in schools or workplaces?
- Which measures mentioned in the text do you find most effective?
- Can you think of a real-life example that relates to the text?

b) Independent literature search in academic databases (e. g. ERIC, Web of Science)

 Task: Conduct research in academic databases and select three additional texts aligned with your interests.

Recommended databases:

• **Eric**

→ <https://eric.ed.gov/>

Enter search terms like 'diversity and geography'.

• **Web of Science**

→ [https://clarivate.com/](https://clarivate.com/products/web-of-science/)

[products/web-of-science/](https://clarivate.com/products/web-of-science/)

Use the questions provided to systematically explore the texts. To what extent have you expanded your conceptual understanding? What new questions have emerged?

c) Explore the glossary – you can also use this toolkit to address open questions.

A Glossary of Key Terms:

→ <https://v-geoscienced.v-global.eu/glossary/>

GLOSSARY

2.2 Intended Curriculum

- ➔ **Topic:** Implementation of diversity-sensitive content and promotion of inclusion into curricula
- 🔄 **Objective:** Integrating diversity-sensitive content and inclusive approaches into curricula prepares future teachers for increasingly diverse and inclusive education systems.

According to Keeves (1992), international curricula exist at three levels: the intended curriculum (official content and objectives), the implemented curriculum (what happens in the classroom), and the achieved curriculum (what students have learned). The second column of the guideline refers to the intended curriculum.

- 📝 **Tasks:** The following steps can be undertaken within the faculty:

1. Analysis of existing curricula

- Review the extent to which Geography and Science curricula account for diversity and inclusion.
- Identify areas where these topics are missing or inadequately addressed.

2. Development of curricular components

- Create learning objectives that develop skills for addressing diversity and inclusion.
- Define relevant content, topics, and methods to support these objectives. Examples can be found in Section 3 (one for Geography and one for Science).
- **Collaboration with experts:** Work closely with specialists such as Diversity Officers to strengthen implementation of inclusive, diverse content.

2.3 Practice and implementation

→ **Topic: Universal Design for Learning (UDL)**

🔄 **Objective:** Explore and understand effective pedagogies within the UDL framework – a concept for addressing student diversity and designing more inclusive classroom

activities. Recognise the connections between UDL, inclusion, diversity and teaching techniques. Reflect on your own teaching and develop initial ideas for integrating these into your practice.

Universal Design for Learning (UDL)

The following UDL-principles – **Engagement, Representation** and **Action & Expression** – provide a theoretical foundation for designing learning environments that respond to diverse learner needs and preferences.

WHY

The first principle, Engagement,

refers to the why of learning. It highlights the importance of stimulating motivation and sustaining interest through multiple means of participation. In the context of a VFT, this involves offering flexible entry points – such as videos, audio narratives, or interactive maps – that appeal to different learning preferences and emotional connections. By doing so, teachers promote affective learning, ensuring that students feel involved and curious throughout the experience.

WHAT

The second principle, Representation,

concerns the what of learning. It focuses on presenting content in diverse formats to support sustainable learning. This can be achieved by integrating multiple modes of representation – visual, textual, auditory, and interactive – so that all students can access content in a way that aligns with their cognitive and sensory strengths. Providing flexible ways of presenting information helps guarantee that no learner is excluded due to format or modality barriers.

HOW

Finally, Action and Expression,

the how of learning, emphasises allowing learners to demonstrate what they know through multiple forms of response. This might include completing quizzes, creating digital artifacts such as maps or photos, or contributing reflections through written, oral, or multimedia formats. These varied opportunities support strategic learning and empower students to express understanding using methods that align with their skills and preferences.

In sum, applying the UDL principles to any subject contributes to creating **inclusive, flexible, and motivating learning environments**. Such integration ensures that all students, regardless of background, ability, or learning preferences, can meaningfully engage with the experience, access content in multiple ways, and demonstrate their learning effectively.

 Task:

1. Reflect on your own teaching practice

and discuss central challenges with colleagues (Think-Pair-Share)

- How diverse are the learners in your classroom?
- In which situations do students struggle despite your efforts?
- Who usually needs “extra support” in your lessons – and why?
- Work together to compile a list of key classroom challenges.

2. Explore the concept of UDL using the definition (see the box on page 13) and a key text: Hall, T. E., Meyer, A., & Rose, D. H. (2024). *Universal Design for Learning in the Classroom: Practical Applications for K-12 and Beyond 2nd Edition*. New York.

Discuss the following questions in your group:

- What added value does Universal Design for Learning bring to teaching practice?
- Which assumptions about learners does UDL challenge?
- How can you put engagement, representation and action & expression into your practice?
- How does UDL change the way we think and act regarding learning difficulties?

3. Reflect on your own teaching and possible UDL applications or implementation options.

Discuss the following questions in groups:

- Which UDL principles are already present in your teaching?
- Where do you see the greatest potential for change?
- Which barriers (time, resources, assessment, structures) are mentioned in the text or experienced in practice?

Select a specific teaching scenario

(e. g. introducing a new topic, using an assessment, adjusting the pace of work) and develop it further using UDL:

- How can learner engagement be increased?
- How can content be represented in different ways?
- How can students demonstrate their learning in different formats?

Future Plans

- Select one UDL idea you would like to use.
- What support would you need to implement UDL more consistently?

2.4 Evaluation

The evaluation should examine the extent to which teachers understand the guideline's content and recommendations, together with the challenges of implementing them in practice. It should assess the degree of acceptance and the actual effectiveness of the measures.

Recommended methods:

- **Qualitative interviews or focus groups:** These provide insights into teachers' individual experiences with the guideline
- **Classroom or seminar observations and peer-to-peer feedback**
- **Document analysis** (e. g., of teaching materials or curricula) to review the implementation of diversity and inclusion at institutional level (e. g., schools or teacher training)

- **Quantitative approaches** such as questionnaires or written feedback, which provide statistical data to measure dissemination, acceptance, and change

Results from this feedback will play a central role in further developing and adapting these guidelines. To support this, a summary report should be compiled to outline the strengths, weaknesses, and any specific recommended actions identified.

After this evaluation, it is important to reflect on these results to ensure long-term success and sustainability of these measures. Therefore, through this structured, and continuous evaluation, it will facilitate practices to become increasingly diversity-sensitive and inclusive.

3

Case Studies for Geography and Science Education

The following section presents two case studies illustrating how Universal Design for Learning (UDL) can be implemented in geography education and science education. In the case of geography education, this is done through map work and virtual field trips; in science education, through the topic of chocolate.

3.1 Geography Education

To ensure inclusive and accessible geography education, materials and learning environments must be designed using UDL principles to meet diverse learning needs. This can be achieved by using a variety of media and presentation formats that accommodate students' differing perceptual and engagement preferences. For example, learning materials should be available

in multiple accessible formats, including text, audio, video, interactive maps, and graphics. Courses should be designed so students can choose how they access content, for example by using digital platforms offering accessible resources. The following specific activities are recommended:

Case 1: Mapwork: Exploring a selected neighbourhood (based on UDL principles)

 Objective: Students explore, understand, and present the special features of their selected neighbourhood

Materials:

- Analogue and digital maps
- Tactile maps
- Various task and information cards (text, images, videos, audio)
- Creative presentation formats (posters, videos)

1. Multiple Means of Engagement

WHY students learn

Start: Look at an analogue or digital map of a place (e. g. city neighbourhood).

 Task: What geographical features can you identify?

2. Multiple Means of Representation

WHAT content students learn

This UDL-based mapwork allows everyone to choose their own approach to exploring their selected neighbourhood, using creative and diverse presentation formats. It promotes active learning by drawing on individual strengths, motivation, and lasting understanding. Information is provided through:

- Analogue maps (eg. school atlases or topographic maps)
- Digital maps
- Tactile maps
- 3D topography (eg. virtual sandboxes)

Tactile maps

Tactile maps (figure 2) empower students with visual impairments or blindness to fully engage with lessons. By exploring these maps through touch, they can physically feel the raised relief maps to understand spatial concepts and deepen their grasp of geographical content.

3D tactile maps can be created by using OpenStreetMap data and a 3D printer. This involves converting geographic data (e. g. locations or addresses) into digital format, then modelling it to represent map elements in three dimensions. Floor plans are extruded to create elevated building profiles, while water areas are distinguished by surface textures. The resulting

Figure 2: 3D Tactile map

3D model is printed in layers – which may take several hours – producing detailed representations of key landmarks (buildings, roads, footpaths, pavements and railway lines). Rivers and lakes are also clearly recognisable by their surface textures. This method produces detailed 3D tactile maps that enhance spatial orientation.

You can find the available providers online.

3D topography: Designing a landscape in a virtual sandbox

In this Augmented Reality (AR) sandbox activity, users shape the sand into landscape features. A depth camera captures this in real time by continuously measuring sand heights to generate a digital terrain model. A projector then displays this data onto the sand surface as coloured elevation levels, contour lines, or simulated water. This creates a direct link between physical manipulation and the digital visualisation, with every change in the sand instantly updating the projected landscape, making topographical concepts intuitively tangible.

3. Multiple Means of Action and Expression

HOW students show learning

Students should choose how to demonstrate their learning:

- **Presentation:** Create a digital poster, Power-Point presentation, or short video about the neighbourhood.
- **Report:** Write a short report or guide.
- **Audio / podcast:** Record a short podcast sharing key findings.
- **Creative work:** create a photo story.

Support provided:

- Language explanations
- Word lists
- Translations

Assessment

- Observation during activities
- Self-assessment using smiley scales
- Teacher feedback focused on understanding and learning goals

Case 2: Virtual field trips based on UDL principles

→ Topic: Virtual field trip

Subject: Geography

Grade: 5 – 12

🔄 Learning Goals

- Accessible exploration of a location in virtual spaces
- Understanding physical and human geographical characteristics of places
- Development of individual research questions
- Application of scientific methods

Virtual field trips provide an ideal way to make outdoor learning experiences accessible to all students, including those unable to participate physically, as Sprenger et al. (2025) and Sprenger, Scholten & Caldis (2024), have highlighted. However, designing them from a UDL perspective, requires presenting content through varied formats using images, digital maps and interactive 360° videos, that students can access individually. This approach ensures all students, regardless of their specific needs, can explore and engage with the material.

To support this, varied access options should be provided, including subtitles, audio descriptions and simplified language versions. Tasks and questions should also allow multiple response formats (written, visual, or oral), to utilise individual strengths.

Figure 4: Inclusive Virtual field trip | Source: → *Peat bogs. Witnesses of the ice age – future*

Steps based on UDL Principles

1. Multiple Means of Engagement

WHY students learn

- Start with a brief 360° tour of the virtual field trip to get a first impression.
- Collect questions based on first impressions:
“What do you think we are exploring here?”
“What phenomena could be interesting here?”
- Offer a choice of content: Students then develop their own questions (with teacher support where needed), such as:
 - What geographical characteristics (physical or human) define the moor?
 - What is the significance of the moor?
 - How is the land around the moor used?
 - How does the moor compare to other moors?
- Offer a choice of working methods (e. g. individually, in pairs or in groups)

2. Multiple Means of Representation

WHAT content students learn

- Interactive virtual field trip through the moor.
- Multimedia content:
 - Videos
 - Audio files (e. g. birdsong, interviews).
 - Images of the moor and infographics (with alternative text)
 - Reading material: short texts, multilingual texts, and texts for different reading levels (including simple language).
 - Data and maps (with alternative text)

3. Multiple Means of Action and Expression

HOW students show learning

Students choose **one** of the following of tasks:

- Creation of a digital poster or presentation addressing their research questions
- Video or audio reports presenting their findings

Support is provided through:

- Online tools (e. g. Padlet or TaskCard) for creative expression.
- Language explanations
- Word lists
- Translations

Assessment

- Observation during activities
- Self-assessment using smiley scales
- Teacher feedback focused on understanding and learning goals

3.2 Science Education

→ **Topic:** Chocolate

Subject: Primary Science / Social Studies
(General Studies)

Grade: 3 – 4

🎯 **Learning Goals**

Students will:

- Find out the ingredients in different chocolates
- Understand where chocolate comes from and how it is produced
- Learn key facts about cocoa plants and chocolate production
- Reflect on social and environmental aspects (e. g. fair trade)

1. Multiple Means of Engagement

WHY students learn

Goal: Motivate learners by connecting to their interests.

Introduction

- Start with a piece of chocolate that students can see, smell and taste.
- Tasting activity with different types of chocolate (milk, dark, white, with nuts etc.).
- Show pictures and packaging from everyday life, or a short promotional video.
- Classroom discussion: “When do you eat chocolate?”, “Where do you think chocolate comes from?”
- Students develop own questions to explore, e. g.:
 - Where does chocolate come from?
 - How is chocolate made?
 - Who works with cocoa?
 - Is chocolate healthy?
- Choice offered:
 - Students choose a question to explore
 - Choice of working methods: individual, pair or group work.

2. Multiple Means of Representation

WHAT content students learn

Goal: Present information in different ways.

Case 1: Where does chocolate come from?

Information is provided through:

- A short, animated video showing the journey from cocoa bean on the plantation to a chocolate bar in the supermarket
- A cocoa fruit and chocolate nibbles to explore
- Picture cards illustrating the different steps of production and trade routes
- Texts at two reading levels about cocoa plants and cocoa farming
- A podcast about cocoa farming
- A world map highlighting cocoa-growing countries
- A puzzle highlighting cocoa growing countries
- Chocolate bars with different backgrounds (e. g. traditional chocolate, organic, fair trade)
- Key vocabulary (e. g. cocoa bean, harvest, factory, fair trade) is:
 - Illustrated with images
 - Explained orally
 - Displayed on a word wall

Case 2: How is chocolate made and what are the ingredients?

Information is provided through:

- A real cocoa bean and chocolate nibs to explore
- Different chocolate bars (white, milk chocolate, dark chocolate) and the exploration of their ingredient lists
- Picture cards showing the chocolate-making process
- Texts at two reading levels about the steps of production from cocoa fruit to chocolate bar
- A podcast about the production of chocolate bars
- Making your own chocolate bars

3. Multiple Means of Action and Expression

HOW students show learning

Goal: Allow different ways to demonstrate understanding.

Students choose **one** of the following tasks:

- Draw and label the steps of chocolate production
- Record a short oral explanation (audio or video)
- Build the process using pictures or blocks in sequence
- Write a short text or create a mini booklet
- Act out the journey of a cocoa bean in a small role play

Support is provided through:

- Step-by-step checklists
- Sentence starters (scaffolding for language use)
- Word lists

Assessment

- Observation during group work
- Self-assessment using smiley scales
- Teacher feedback focused on understanding and learning goals

4

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